

DETECÇÃO DE FALHAS EM ROLAMENTOS VIA REDES NEURAIAS CONVOLUCIONAIS USANDO ACELERÔMETROS MEMS DE BAIXO CUSTO.

BEARING FAULT DETECTION VIA CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS USING LOW-COST MEMS ACCELEROMETERS

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Resumo: O estudo foca na detecção de falhas em rolamentos em ambientes industriais, que são cruciais para o desempenho e a confiabilidade dos equipamentos. A utilização de acelerômetros comerciais para a aquisição de sinais de falhas é cara, o que limita sua implementação em equipamentos em série. As redes neurais convolucionais (CNN) surgiram como um método promissor para detecção de falhas, mas esse método não funciona bem com dados unidimensionais. Para resolver esse problema, o estudo propõe a avaliação de dois acelerômetros de sistemas microeletromecânicos (MEMS) de baixo custo para obter sinais de vibração e convertê-los em imagens 2D para análise por CNN. Uma plataforma experimental foi construída, conectando os acelerômetros MPU6050 e ADXL345 a rolamentos em condições normais e com falhas. Imagens das assinaturas de vibração foram inseridas nas CNN com dimensões de 16x16, 22x22 e 28x28 para avaliar seu impacto na precisão. Os resultados mostraram que o algoritmo proposto alcançou alta precisão: para o MPU6050, 97,31% de precisão com imagens 16x16, 96,95% com 22x22 e 98,92% com 28x28; para o ADXL345, 98,31% com imagens 16x16, 99,70% com 22x22 e 99,82% com 28x28. Este trabalho demonstra a eficácia dos acelerômetros de baixo custo e da conversão de imagens 2D para melhorar a detecção de falhas em rolamentos.

Palavras-chave: Rede Neural Convolucional. Acelerômetro MEMS de baixo custo. Detecção de falhas em rolamentos.

Abstract: *The study focuses on detecting bearing failures in industrial environments, crucial to equipment performance and reliability. Commercial accelerometers used for fault signal acquisition are expensive, limiting their implementation in serial equipment. Convolutional neural networks (CNN) have emerged as an emerging method for fault detection, but this method does not work well with one-dimensional data. To address this, the study proposes evaluating two low-cost microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) accelerometers for obtaining vibration signals and converting them into 2D images for CNN analysis. An experimental platform was built, connecting the MPU6050 and ADXL345 accelerometers to bearings with normal and faulty conditions. Vibration signature images were inserted into CNN with dimensions of 16x16, 22x22, and 28x28 to assess their impact on accuracy. The results showed that the proposed algorithm achieved high accuracy: for MPU6050, 97,31% accuracy with 16x16 images, 96,95% with 22x22 and 98,92% with 28x28, for ADXL345, 98,31% with 16x16 images, 99,70% with 22x22 and 99,82% with 28x28. This research demonstrates the effectiveness of low-cost*

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accelerometers and 2D image conversion to improve bearing failure detection.

Keywords: Convolutional neural network. Low-cost MEMS accelerometer. Bearing failure detection.

I. INTRODUCTION

In modern industries, rotating machines represent over 90% of the equipment used (HAN et al., 2021). Rotating machines encompass a wide variety of equipment such as motors, compressors, mechanical spindles, and mechanical transmission boxes (DI et al., 2020). Being one of the main machine elements that make up a rotating machine, the bearing is intended to support axial and radial loads, as well as to reduce rotational friction with the shaft (WANG et al., 2019).

In general, rotating machines are used for long periods and in complex and variable workload environments, because of this, bearings are constantly subject to early mechanical wear (DEVECI et al., 2021). This characteristic makes bearings identified as a critical element representing approximately 55% of failures in rotating machines (DUAN et al., 2019). When bearings fail unexpectedly, they can cause significant damage to the equipment, with high repair and replacement costs, in addition to causing production stoppages, directly impacting the operational efficiency of the equipment, causing significant economic losses for companies (DE SOUZA, 2022). Therefore, to ensure greater reliability of rotating machines, the monitoring of rolling bearings is of great importance, for which it is necessary to use accurate and fast methods for diagnosing the real state of the equipment.

Despite the wide range of approaches that can be used in applications to monitor the state of equipment (SILVA JUNIOR, 2021), the analysis of vibration signals is the most used technique to determine the mechanical the machine, as this is one of the first symptoms of perceived degradation, it is usually followed by noise, heat and finally smoke (EULDJI et al., 2021). The development of low-cost technology in

the manufacture of micro-electro-mechanical systems (MEMS) has spread the use of this type of sensor for the analysis of vibration signals (FERNANDES, 2023).

Given the relevance, the theme of this work arises from the proposal to evaluate and compare the use of low-cost MEMS-type accelerometers applied to the prediction of rolling element defects and outer race defects in bearings.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experimental bench to be used was made on the campus of the Federal Institute of Education, Science, and Technology of São Paulo, and has some materials donated by partner companies CESTARI-WEG and Schneider Electric, the bench has a gearmotor connected to two bearings through an elastic coupler and machined 1020 steel shaft. Figure 1 shows the workbench and the elements that compose it.

Figure 1 – Experimental bench.

Source: Author,2024.

The geared motor used has a 3 HP three-phase induction motor with a nominal speed of 1780 RPM connected to the reduction input, the internal gear arrangement provides a reduction of 48.90 times resulting in an output speed of 36.8 RPM with 400 Nm of torque when the engine is at rated speed. To allow the collection of data in different conditions of use, the experimental bench has a control panel with a frequency inverter allowing the variation of motor

rotation, as well as the selection of the direction of rotation.

For carrying out the experiments, four NSK spherical roller bearings, model 21306CD, were used. This specific bearing has as its main features a high operating load capacity, pressed steel cage, and permissible misalignment between 1° and 2.5° in normal load situations. Of the four bearings chosen for the study, two remained unchanged, maintaining their original characteristics. The other two were segregated for manual insertion of defects, one bearing for roller defect and one bearing for outer race defect, respectively. Figure 2 shows the open bearings coupled to the driven shaft, is possible to notice that the top of the cover of each bearing was milled to facilitate the subsequent assembly of the accelerometers.

Figure 2 – Mechanical assembly of bearings on the experimental bench.

Source: Author,2024.

For this experiment, the sensors chosen were the accelerometers MPU6050 and ADXL345, given their low cost (US \$10 and US \$5 respectively) and easy application due to their already digitized outputs. Both are MEMS-type triaxial accelerometers that can be adjusted by the user via programming to operate at $\pm 2g$, $\pm 4g$, $\pm 8g$, and $\pm 16g$. Table 1 shows a comparison between the main characteristics of the MPU6050 and ADXL345 accelerometers. As the communication interface of the accelerometers takes place through the PC serial, it is necessary to use a controller that can perform the readings, for which the ESP-32 microcontroller was chosen due to its low market cost and sufficient performance for the application. To

minimize possible interference between the microcontroller and the accelerometer as much as possible, it was decided to solder the accelerometer to a standard island-type board and connect the microcontroller to this board through a socket

Table 1 – Comparison between MPU6050 and ADXL345.

Features	MPU6050	ADXL345
Price	US \$10	US \$5
Power supply	3.3 to 5 V	3.3 to 5 V
Supply voltage	500 μ A	140 μ A
Non-linearity	0.2%	0.5%
Operating temperature	40 to +85 °C	40 to +85 °C
Communication interface	I ² C	I ² C

Source: Author,2024.

To attach the microcontroller/sensor assembly to the bearing, a box with a base magnetized by neodymium magnets was developed and printed in 3D. Finally, Figure 3 shows the set mounted on the case coupled to the accelerometer during an acquisition.

Figure 3 – Sensor connected to the bearing during an acquisition

Source: Author,2024.

For signal acquisition, bearing 1 always used the sample in good condition, and bearing 2 varied between samples in good condition, roller defect, and outer race defect. Four shaft rotation speeds were used for each bearing sample 2, being obtained when the inverter was set at 45, 60, 75, and 90 Hz. Table 2 shows a summary of all twelve combinations of acquisition scenarios set by default. For the data to be

acquired in the most uniform way possible, an experimental procedure for data collection was also developed, allowing all measurements were always carried out in the same order of execution for both sensors in all speed ranges. Table 3 shows the experimental procedure adopted.

Table 2 – Scenarios for signal acquisition

Acquisition scenario	Inverter frequency (Hz)	Output rotation (RPM)	Bearing 2 condition
1	45	27.8	Good
2	60	36.7	Good
3	75	46.0	Good
4	90	54.8	Good
5	45	27.8	Roller defect
6	60	36.7	Roller defect
7	75	46.0	Roller defect
8	90	54.8	Roller defect
9	45	27.8	Outer race defect.
10	60	36.7	Outer race defect.
11	75	46.0	Outer race defect.
12	90	54.8	Outer race defect

Source: Author,2024.

Table 3 – Experimental procedure for signal acquisition on the experimental bench

Step	Task
1	30 minutes warm-up
2	Set inverter to LSP=45 and HSP=60
3	Collect data counterclockwise at 45 Hz with the ADXL345 accelerometer for 30 min and save
4	Collect data counterclockwise at 60 Hz with the ADXL345 accelerometer for 30 min and save
5	Set inverter to LSP=75 and HSP=90
6	Collect data counterclockwise at 75 Hz with the ADXL345 accelerometer for 30 min and save
7	Collect data counterclockwise at 90 Hz with the ADXL345 accelerometer for 30 min and save
8	Change the sensor
9	Collect data counterclockwise at 90 Hz with the MPU6050 accelerometer for 30 min and save
10	Collect data counterclockwise at 75 Hz with the MPU6050 accelerometer for 30 min and save
11	Set inverter to LSP=45 and HSP=60
12	Collect data counterclockwise at 60 Hz with the MPU6050 accelerometer for 30 min and save

- 13 Collect data counterclockwise at 45 Hz with the MPU6050 accelerometer for 30 min and save
- 14 Change the bearing 2 sample and repeat the tests

Source: Author,2024.

In Figure 4, a temporal vibration signal can be seen in a 10-second window obtained through the signals collected by the MPU6050 accelerometer for the three respective bearing samples.

Figure 4 – Vibration signal acquired by the MPU6050 sensor for the three bearing samples.

Source: Author,2024.

To extract the maximum performance from the network algorithm, the temporal data of one dimension were converted into vectors of two dimensions in grayscale. To convert temporal data into images, they were first normalized to values between 0 and 1 and then grouped into a 2D matrix (SAYED et al., 2023).

For the pixels to be grouped, the signal must be windowed using a specific length to be determined by the number of pixels needed to obtain the image. this offset can be greater than, less than, or equal to the window length and is userdefined.

For the present work, the temporal signals were converted to three dimensions of predefined images, to compare the influence of image dimensionality on the accuracy of the algorithm. Table 4 shows the dimensions, the window length, and the step adopted for each of the defined image dimensions, as well as the total size of the dataset with the data collected by the accelerometers.

In the adopted convolutional network configuration, the first layer added is a convolutional layer with 32 filters and a kernel size of 3x3, with the ReLU activation function. The input of the convolutional layer is defined by the size of the image that enters the algorithm. The second layer added is a maximum pooling layer with a 2x2 window and a 2x2 step responsible for reducing the image dimension. The third layer added is another convolutional layer with 64 filters and a kernel size of 3x3, with the ReLU activation function. The fourth layer added is another maximum pooling layer with a 2x2 window and a 2x2 pitch, responsible for again reducing the image dimension. The fifth layer added is a flattened layer, which transforms the output of the previous layer into a one-dimensional vector. The added sixth layer is a fully connected dense layer with 128 neurons and the ReLU activation function. The seventh and last layer added is another dense layer with 3 neurons (equal to the number of classes N, R, and PE), and the Softmax activation function to generate the probabilities of each class. Table 5 shows the structure of the configuration.

Table 4 - Dimensions, window length, stride, and number of images for data collected with accelerometers.

Accelerometer	Image Size	Number of images generated
MPU6050	28x28	16434
MPU6050	22x22	21070
MPU6050	16x16	41089
ADXL345	28x28	23290
ADXL345	22x22	29861
ADXL345	16x16	58232

Source: Author,2024.

Table 5 – The parameters of the constructed CNN.

Layer	Type	Neurons/Filters	Kernel	Activation Function
1	Conv2D	32	(3.3)	ReLU
2	MaxPooling2D	-	(2.2)	-
3	Conv2D	64	(3.3)	ReLU
4	MaxPooling2D	-	(2.2)	-
5	Flatten	-	-	-
6	Dense	128	-	ReLU
7	Dense	3	-	Softmax

Source: Author,2024.

The batch size was set to 200, which means that the model updates the weights after every batch of 200 training examples. The number of epochs was set to 20, which means that the model will run through the entire training dataset 20 times. Training data were randomized before each epoch. The configuration was compiled with the categorical crossentropy loss function and the Adam optimizer.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The proposed network configuration was tested for the classification of failures in bearings taking as input the 16x16, 22x22, and 28x28 images generated through the data collected by the accelerometers MPU6050 and ADXL345.

Figure 5 shows the results of network training for fault classification with 28x28 images from the MPU6050 accelerometer. In blue is the training curve and in orange is the validation curve both as a function of the number of epochs. It can be observed that the accuracy of the model increases rapidly in the first epochs, in addition, the accuracy in the validation set closely follows the accuracy in the training set, indicating that the model is not suffering from overfitting, this pattern was repeated for the other samples tested.

Figure 5 – Model accuracy using 28x28 images generated from data collected by the MPU 6050 accelerometer

Source: Author,2024.

In the graphical matrices obtained from the signals of the accelerometers, it was noted that most of the model's predictions are located on the main diagonal, indicating that the model correctly classified the majority of the samples in the dataset. Additionally, except for the confusion matrix presented in Figure B, the PE class appears lighter than the other areas, suggesting that the model achieved the highest success rate for this class. Furthermore, the matrices also reveal that for both accelerometers, the larger the image size, the more accurate the classification.

Table 6 shows the accuracy of both accelerometers for the different dimensions of the tested images, it can be noted that both sensors showed promising results, it is also possible to observe that despite being cheaper, the ADXL345 accelerometer performed better when compared to the MPU6050 under the same conditions.

Table 6 – The accuracy obtained with the adopted network configuration.

Layer	Image dimension	Train data accuracy (%)	Test data accuracy (%)
MPU6050	28x28	99.29	98.92
MPU6050	22x22	97.74	96.95
MPU6050	16x16	97.96	97.31
ADXL345	28x28	100	99.82
ADXL345	22x22	100	99.70
ADXL345	16x16	99.98	98.31

Source: Author,2024.

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study highlights the importance of detecting bearing faults in the industrial field and addresses the limitations of expensive commercial accelerometers by proposing the use of low-cost MEMS accelerometers. By converting the obtained vibration signals into 2D images and applying convolutional neural networks (CNN), the proposed algorithm effectively identifies and classifies subtle characteristics of bearing signals. The experimental results demonstrate high accuracy across different image dimensions, showcasing the potential

of this approach. The research provides valuable insights into the feasibility of implementing cost-effective fault detection methods in serial equipment. By enabling more accessible and reliable fault detection, this study contributes to improving the performance and reliability of mechanical equipment in various industrial applications. The findings encourage further exploration of low-cost sensor technologies and their integration with advanced machine-learning techniques for enhanced fault detection and preventive maintenance strategies in the industry. In future works, this type of approach has the potential to be applied in the detection of other types of failures in mechanical systems, such as, for example, the detection of failures in gear sets and the detection of misalignments in rotating equipment, in these cases it should prior training with the data of the respective expected failures should be carried out, to provide parameters for the machine learning of these new failure modes. It is also possible to highlight the possibility of implanting the learning algorithm already pre-trained in low-cost microprocessors (tinyML), allowing the diagnosis to be made locally without the need to process information in a cloud server, thus replacing the excessive sending of raw data to the server by the result of the equipment diagnostics

V. REFERÊNCIAS

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